

English literature of 19th century.(Realism)

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Annotatsiya: Hozirgi asr boshlari yozuvchilari Nitsshe, Kant va Shopengauer kabi faylasuflardan juda ta'sirlangan; va shuning uchun ularning asarlarini falsafiy tadqiqotlarning bir turi deb hisoblash mumkin. Maugham ham bundan mustasno emas edi. Ushbu maqolada, tanqidchilar Maughamga nisbatan adolatsizlik qilgani va u juda sermahsul yozuvchi ekanligi , asarlari orasida yaxshi va yomon romanlar bor ekanligi takidlangani haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'p asarlar yaratgan yozuvchi, realizm tushunchasi, butunlay rad etilgan

Abstract: Early modern writers were greatly influenced by philosophers such as Nietzsche, Kant, and Schopenhauer; and therefore their works can be considered a kind of philosophical research. Maugham was no exception. This article argues that critics have been unfair to Maugham and that he was a very prolific writer, with good and bad novels among his works.

Key words: prolific writer, the concept of realism, totally rejected

Queen Victoria's reign lasted until 1901 and the literature that was being produced closer to the turn of the century shared few characteristics with the earlier works of the Victorian Era. Those writers at the end of the Victorian Era such as Oscar Wilde and Thomas Hardy. The novelists at the turn of the century continued

to explore the problems in English social life, but explored other key themes as well. The greatest departure from the early Victorian era came from these authors exploration of themes such as sexuality and a focus on the ways in which science and technology would revolutionize the world in the upcoming century.

Realism began as a literary movement in response to and as a departure from the idealism of the Romantic period. Realism emerged in literature in the second half of the nineteenth century, most predominantly in novels. Realism was characterized by its attention to detail, as well as its attempt to recreate reality as it was. As a result, plot was no longer the central to the focus of the author, but rather creating interesting and complex characters took precedence. Realism also placed an emphasis on describing the material and physical details of life, as opposed to the natural world as characterized by the Romantic period. Many Realistic novelists veered away from the softer aspects of Romanticism, such as intense tenderness and idealism, because they believed those characteristics misrepresented the harsh realities of life. Realism emphasizes accurate descriptions of setting, dress, and character in ways that would have appeared inappropriate to earlier authors. Realism, which emphasizes the importance of the ordinary person and the ordinary situation, generally rejects the heroic and the aristocratic and embraces the ordinary working class citizen.¹

The publication in 1859 of Charles Darwin's *On the Origin of Species* which put the existence of God into radical question. Across the whole population, and in the face of rapid economic and social changes, radical doubts about the stability of the existing order were expressed.

¹ Paul DOTTIN, 'The Realism of Somerset Maugham: The Painted Veil', in *The Maugham Enigma*, p.145.

The time of the First World War (1914-1918) there was a whole new generation of young soldiers who not only could read but, very important, were able for the first time in the history of war to write letters home describing war in all its unheroic horror.

The term **Aestheticism** comes from the Greek word meaning "*to perceive*" or "*to feel*". It is a late 19th-century European arts movement that centered on the doctrine that *art exists for the sake of its beauty alone*. It began in reaction to prevailing utilitarian **social philosophies** and to the perceived **ugliness of the industrial age**. Its philosophical foundations were laid by **Immanuel Kant**, who separated the sense of beauty from practical interests. Aesthetes believed *that sensation should be the source of art*, and that the role of the artist was to make the public share his feelings. The Aesthetic movement's insistence on '**Art for Art's sake**' was just as much a search for new values as any philosophical or political movement, but its values and motivations have been called into question through the fate of Oscar Wilde.

They *totally rejected* the *Victorian notion* that art should have a *moral, social or political purpose*, believing that artist should care about form and technique and express himself freely: he should not become the slave of fixed moral and ethical conventions.

Decadent movement in literature, or **Decadence**, was closely associated with the doctrines of Aestheticism. In **France**, decadence became almost synonymous with the work of the *Symbolists* who wrote in reaction against *realism and naturalism*.

Designed to convey impressions by suggestion rather than by direct statement, **Symbolism** found its first expression in poetry but was later extended to

realistic novel. His realism is expressed not only in his realistic method of writing but also in his view of life itself. I think *The Summing Up* is the record in which he wrote the realistic process in his literary life in some sense. By the way, his objective realism turned its edge to the common-sense in its conventional meaning that is the virtue of the middle class. In Maugham's mind what seemed to be virtue, is nothing but the conventional custom and habit respecting the social respectability or the thing that shadows the falsehood and imposture. The critical mind which originally comes from the good sense, broke the harmony with the moderation supporting the good sense itself.

The name of Somerset Maugham is connected with critical realism in the English literature of the first decades of the 20th century. He possessed a keen and observant eye and in his best works he ridiculed hypocrisy, self-interest, utilitarian approach to art. W.S Maugham was a prolific writer. Numerous novels, short stories and plays came from his pen. His best novels are: *Of Human Bondage*, *The Moon and Sixpence*, *Cakes and Ale*. At his best he is an incomparable story-teller. He writes with lucidity and almost ostentatious simplicity. His acid irony and brilliant style helped him win a huge audience of readers.

The author's style is clear and precise. He doesn't impose his views on the reader. He puts a question and leaves it to the reader to answer it. When criticizing something he sounds rather amused than otherwise. Maugham's brilliant style made his books extremely popular all over the world.

References:

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